

The throwing angle to maximum throwing range:

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We introduce:

α = throwing angle $0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$

V_0 = initial velocity

g = earth acceleration

m = mass of the ball

t = time

$$C = \arctan\left(\sqrt{\frac{r}{m \cdot g}} \cdot V_0 \sin \alpha\right)$$

$F(v) = r \cdot v^2$ is the resistance force in gas with the velocity v .

From [1] we know the throwing range:

$$W = X(t_w) = \frac{m}{r} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{r V_0 \cos \alpha}{m} \cdot t_w + 1\right)$$

with:

$$t_w = \sqrt{\frac{m}{r g}} \cdot \left(\cosh^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{\cos \alpha}\right) + C\right)$$

chain rule:

$$0 = \frac{dW}{d\alpha} = \frac{m}{r} \cdot \left(\frac{r V_0 \cos \alpha}{m} \cdot t_w + 1\right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\frac{r V_0 \cos \alpha}{m} \cdot \frac{dt_w}{d\alpha} - \frac{r V_0 \sin \alpha}{m} \cdot t_w\right) \quad \text{I}$$

with:

$$\frac{dt_w}{dd} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{rg}} \cdot \left(\frac{(-1) \cdot (\cos C)^{-2} \cdot \frac{d \cos C}{dd}}{\pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{\cos C}\right)^2 - 1}} + \frac{dC}{dd} \right)$$

and

$$C = \arctan \left(\sqrt{\frac{r}{m \cdot g}} \cdot v_0 \sin d \right)$$

it follows:

$$\frac{d \cos C}{dd} = (-\sin C) \cdot \frac{dC}{dd}$$

$$\frac{dC}{dd} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{r}{m \cdot g}} \cdot v_0 \cdot \cos d}{1 + \frac{r (v_0 \cdot \sin d)^2}{m \cdot g}}$$

Then the differentiation is completed.

Solving the equation (I) to d and we get the wanted throwing angle.

We view an example with initial velocity from 20m/sec. The ball's diameter is 10 cm. The initial height is 0m.

The tabular shows: The searched throwing angles is different from 45 degree. In this example the gas is air:

Mass of the ball in kg	Throwing angle to maximum throwing range in degree	Throwing time in seconds	Maximum throwing range in metres	Height of ascent in metres
0,01	33,6	1,25	7,252	2,04
0,1	41,2	2,31	24,649	6,62
1,0	44,4	2,80	37,937	9,60
5,0	44,8	2,86	40,173	10,04
10,0	44,9	2,87	40,471	10,12

[1] Harald Schröder „The inclined throw in a medium (gas,air) with larger distances“ 2015 Zenodo